

Comparative analysis between Flipped-learning and Guided-Discovery Strategies on Achievement in Chemistry among Secondary School Students in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the comparative analysis of flipped-learning and guided-discovery learning strategies on achievement in chemistry among secondary school students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The design was a quasi-experimental design of pre-test, posttest research. Population composed of all senior secondary two (SS2) Chemistry students in the 13 co-educational schools in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 2 schools for the study. The sample size was 80 senior secondary two (SS2) Chemistry students in 2 intact classes. Researchers adopted instrument tagged Chemical Bonding Achievement Test (CBAT) was used to collect data. Reliability of the instrument was found to be 0.82 using Kuder Richardson formula-20. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions, while the hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance. Findings of the study showed that students taught the concept of chemical bonding using guided-discovery strategy performed better than those taught using flipped-learning strategy. There was a significant difference in the achievement mean scores of students taught using guided-discovery and flipped-learning strategies. But there was no significant difference and interaction effect between the mean achievements scores of male and female students. It was recommended among others that teachers of Chemistry should deploy guided discovery learning strategy in teaching chemical bonding in Chemistry to enhance students' achievement.

Keyword: Flipped-learning, Guided-discovery, Chemical Bonding, Achievement and Gender

Introduction

Chemistry is one branch of natural science. Chemistry deals with every aspect of daily life, such as food, drink, clothing, medicine, housing, vehicles, and many others. Chemistry explained a lot about the phenomena that occur in everyday life; therefore, chemistry cannot be separated from nature. Chemistry helped people solve many difficult life problems; played a vital role in the development of drugs which are used to cure and alleviate diseases and longevity of life (Sylvanus, 2022; Rusmansyah *et al.*, 2019). Chemistry enabled students to provide explanations for almost all natural phenomena they encounter in their daily life or school laboratories. It is also a requirement to study pharmacy, medicine, pharmacy, environmental science, chemical engineering, geology, biology, agriculture and others so on. However, studies have shown that the majority of students at secondary school perceived Chemistry as a difficult subject and this perception become more evasive when they reach university. The decline in academic performance of students in science subjects in secondary school in Nigeria was reported over the years as major concern for the government, teachers, and parents. The poor performance has been attributed to some factors such as students' attitude, scientific attitude, difficult concepts, ineffective classroom instruction, inadequate provision of instructional material, and a lack of academic motivation and self-efficacy (Akpan, 2018; Eden and Mbuk, 2019; Eden, Akpan & Noah, 2024).

The concept of chemical bonding would be required for the understanding of other concepts in Chemistry that has to do with chemical composition of compounds like particulate nature of matter and periodic table which is seen as a difficult concept. This is due to lack of visual representation of bonding concepts, transfer of electrons in all types of bonding. Also, a

continuous spectrum for bonding from covalent to ionic is not demonstrated visually. Therefore, the problems associated with difficulty, misconceptions and lack of understanding of the chemical bonding topic might be associated with the way the chemical bonding is presented and the learning strategies used. Therefore, in this article the chemical bonding topic has been selected to evaluate its sequence of teaching and effectiveness using the flipped learning and guided discovery learning strategies.

Flipped learning strategy is a reversed traditional learning format where the focus was on class time rather than student understanding. It is a learning strategy in which students are introduced to the learning material before classroom time and given opportunity to discussion and find answers to questions. It is an approach in which what is traditionally done in class is being done at home, and that which is done at home is completed in class (Umoetuk and Akpan, 2024). Flipped-learning according to Adonu *et al.*, (2021) is a form of blended learning that combines face-to-face learning in the classroom with group discussion and learning outside of the classroom with video lesson and online collaboration. In a flipped learning environment, the teacher will allow students to take time at home and review the materials, watch videos and carry out other necessary activities related to the topic for the next class before the next lesson. Onwuachu and Okoye (2024) found that the flipped learning strategy provides an archive of teaching resources; an increase in student engagement and a shift from passive listening to active learning.

Moneke and Nwanneka (2023) in a study on effectiveness of guided-inquiry and flipped-learning methods on secondary students' academic achievement found that flipped –learning method significantly improves secondary students' achievement in Ecology compared to guided-inquiry method. The findings also revealed that there is no significant interaction effect of gender and teaching methods on students' academic achievement. Studies by Inengite and Zipomone (2024); Dorji and Dorji (2022) showed that there was a significant impact of flipped learning strategy on students' academic achievement. Umoetuk and Akpan (2023) in a study showed that students taught materials and processing in Basic Technology using flipped classroom strategy gained better than those taught using graphic strategy. Guided-discovery learning strategy on the other hand is a strategy whereby the teacher provides the students with principles, guidelines and procedures that will guide the students on how to find answers or solutions to a problem. According to Ekiugbo (2024) guided discovery learning strategy is a learning situation in which the principal content of learning is not directly exposed by the teacher, but left to be discovered by the learner, making the teacher a guardian and students active participants in the learning process. Guided – discovery requires students to find out things for themselves. This cannot be done where the teaching method is lecture oriented and with an inactive study habit.

A study by Afolabi (2018) on the effect of guided discovery and expository instructional methods on students' transfer of learning found that there was as a significant effect of guided discovery on students' transfer of learning. Oghenov (2018) on the relative effectiveness of guided discovery, demonstration and traditional lecture method of teaching on students' achievement in Biology showed that there was a significant difference between the groups. Ekiugbo (2024) on effects of guided discovery method on students' attitude and achievement showed that students taught using guided-discovery had a higher mean achievement score compared to those taught using discussion and lecture methods. Gender is one of the factors affecting achievement of students in science. Eden and Mbuk (2019) describes gender as term used to describe a person either as a man/boy or a woman/girl, adding that gender is an important factor that contributes to academic performance in Chemistry. Obikezie *et al.*, (2023) defined it as a universally accepted attribute assigned to individuals based on their sexual differences. There are many inconsistencies concerning gender and students' academic performance in Chemistry and science in general. John, Musa and Waziri (2018) found that male students performed better than female students. Ekiugbo (2024); Umanah & Sunday (2022); Eden, Tofi, Umoetuk and Charles (2023); Umoetuk and Akpan, (2024) found that there was no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students when taught Chemistry concepts. Moneke and Nwanneka (2023); Nwuba *et al.*, (2024); Pat-Anyaeji and Okeke, (2019) found that there was a significant gender difference in academic achievement with the females outperforming the males. Based on the literature, it is expedient to investigate into the effectiveness of flipped-learning and guided-discovery learning strategies on the academic achievement of Chemistry students' in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The academic achievement of Chemistry students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, had been a persistent concern, particularly when it comes to complex and technical concepts such as chemical bonding. Chemical bonding, a fundamental concept in Chemistry, requires students to develop a deep understanding of the formation and characteristics of chemical bonds, which can be challenging to grasp due to its abstract and theoretical nature. Traditional teaching methods, which often rely on lectures and rote memorization, have been criticized for being ineffective in promoting deep understanding and retention of this complex concept. As a result, many students struggle to apply theoretical concepts to practical problems, leading to poor academic performance in Chemistry. Furthermore, the technical nature of chemical bonding requires students to develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and

analytical skills, which are often not adequately developed through traditional teaching methods. In light of these challenges, there is a need to investigate alternative instructional strategies that can enhance the academic achievement of Chemistry students, particularly in the context of teaching complex concepts like chemical bonding. Specifically, this study seeks to explore the impact of flipped learning and guided discovery learning strategies on the academic achievement of Chemistry students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, with a focus on the concept of chemical bonding.

Objectives of the study

1. Compare the academic achievement of students taught with flipped-learning with their counterparts taught guided-discovery learning strategies
2. Determine the academic achievements of male and females taught with flipped-learning, and also determine the academic achievement of males and females taught with guided discovery learning strategies
3. Determine the interaction effect of flipped-learning and that of guided discovery learning strategy when used in teaching chemical bonding, and to determine interaction effect of gender on students' academic achievement when taught the concept of chemical bonding with the strategies.

Research Questions

1. What is the difference in the academic achievement of students taught with flipped-learning with their counterparts taught guided-discovery learning strategies?
2. What is the difference in the academic achievements of male and females taught with flipped-learning, and also determine the academic achievement of males and females taught with guided discovery learning strategies?
3. What is the difference in the interaction effect of flipped-learning and that of guided discovery learning strategy when used in teaching chemical bonding, and to determine interaction effect of gender on students' academic achievement when taught the concept of chemical bonding with the strategies?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of students taught with flipped-learning with their counterparts taught guided-discovery learning strategies
2. There is no significant difference in the academic achievements of male and females taught with flipped-learning, and also determine the academic achievement of males and females taught with guided discovery learning strategies
3. There is no significant difference in the interaction effect of flipped-learning and that of guided discovery learning strategy when used in teaching chemical bonding, and to determine interaction effect of gender on students' academic achievement when taught the concept of chemical bonding with the strategies

Methodology

The design of the study is quasi- experimental design with pretest posttest group design. The population of the study comprised of all public co-educational Senior Secondary School two (SSII) students' offering Chemistry in the thirteen (13) public coeducational secondary schools in Uyo Local Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria; with a total enrolment of four thousand and twenty (4,020) students. A sample of eighty (80) Senior Secondary two (SSII) chemistry students from two intact classes were used for the study. The 2 schools were selected by simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was the Chemical Bonding Achievement Test (CBAT), The CBAT was a researcher- made instrument with 30 multiple choice items having four options A, B, C and D with one correct answer and three distractors, the maximum and minimum scores were thirty and zero respectively. The items were drawn from the concept of chemical bonding (covalent bonding, coordinate covalent bonding, ionic bonding, metallic bonding and intermolecular forces of attraction). The CBAT was face and content validated by two experienced chemistry teachers and one expert in test, measurement and evaluation. The validators scrutinized the instrument in terms of: clarity of instrument to the subject, proper wording of items, appropriateness and adequacy of the items for the study. The recommendations by the validators helped to modify the items in the instrument. The final draft of thirty questions were produced from the initial fifty items designed by the researcher. In ascertaining the reliability index of the instrument, copies of the CBAT were administered to a trial test group of thirty (30) SSII chemistry students in the school not selected in the main study but found to be equivalent in all respects to the study area. The result obtained after administration were subjected to Kuder Richardson's formula-20. The result showed a reliability co-efficient value of 0.81. Thus, on the bases of the high reliability index, the CBAT was considered reliable for measuring the students' achievement.

The researchers visited the selected schools and obtained permission from the principal of the schools to use their schools for the study. This was followed by the administration of the CBAT as pre-test on the sample by the researcher. After the pre-test measurements, the researchers taught the groups using the validated lesson notes during their normal Chemistry class period in their intact class settings for three weeks. The students in the experimental group 1 were taught using flipped-learning strategy while those in the experimental group 2 were taught using guided discovery learning strategy where the teacher provides procedures to guide the students helping them to find solutions to the problem. At the end of the learning, the reshuffled version of CBAT was administered as post-test to measure the effects of treatment on students' achievement. The pre-test, and post-test test scripts from the two groups were collected by the researcher for marking and scoring. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question One: What is the difference in the academic achievement of students taught with flipped-learning with their counterparts taught guided-discovery learning strategies?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of students' pretest and posttest achievement mean scores when taught the concept of Chemical bonding using flipped-learning and guided-discovery learning strategies

Groups	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
	N	Mean	SD	Mean	
Flipped-Learning	46	6.17	2.43	31.09	24.92
Guided Discovery	34	5.24	2.49	37.06	31.82

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Results in Table 1 shows the mean difference (posttest-pretest mean scores) for the treatment groups flipped-learning and guided-discovery learning strategies to be 24.92 and 31.82 respectively. This result indicates that students taught the concept of Chemical bonding using guided-discovery learning strategy performed better than those taught using flipped-learning strategy. Table 1 also showed that the standard deviation of students taught Chemical bonding using flipped learning and guided-discovery learning strategies is 4.25 and 4.35 respectively. This indicates that the scattering of scores from the mean scores of students taught Chemical bonding using guided-discovery learning strategy were higher when compared to those taught using flipped-learning strategy.

Research Question Two: What is the difference in the academic achievements of male and females taught with flipped-learning, and also determine the academic achievement of males and females taught with guided discovery learning strategies?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation scores of male and female students taught the concept of chemical bonding using flipped-learning and guided-discovery learning strategies

Groups	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
	N	Mean	SD	Mean	
Flipped-Learning					
Male	24	5.50	2.36	29.00	23.50
Female	22	6.91	2.35	33.36	26.45
Guided-discovery					
Male	18	4.89	2.76	36.11	31.22
Female	16	5.62	2.16	38.13	32.51

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Results in Table 2 show the mean difference (posttest-pretest mean scores) for male students taught the concept of Chemical bonding using flipped-learning and guided-discovery learning strategy is 23.50 and 31.22, respectively while female students taught the concept of bonding using flipped-learning and guided-discovery learning strategy had mean gain scores of 26.45 and 32.5, respectively. This indicates that female students in the Guided-discovery group had the best mean of 32.51 followed by male students in the guided-discovery group.

Research Question Three: What is the difference in the interaction effect of flipped-learning and that of guided discovery learning strategy when used in teaching chemical bonding, and to determine interaction effect of gender on students' academic

achievement when taught the concept of chemical bonding with the strategies? This Research question had a corresponding null hypothesis 3 which was used to answer it.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of students taught with flipped-learning with their counterparts taught guided-discovery learning strategies

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of students' posttest achievement classified by treatment groups (flipped-learning and guided-discovery learning strategies) with pretest as covariate

Source of Variance	Sum of squares	Df	Mean	F	Sig.	Decision at 0.05 alpha
Corrected model	745.55	2	372.77	20.69	0.00	Significant
Pretest (Covariate)	48.33	1	48.33	2.68	0.11	Not Significant
Main effect:						
Learning strategy	742.06	1	742.06	41.19	0.00	Significant
Error	1387.20	77	18.02			
Corrected total	2132.75	79				

Source: Fieldwork, 2024 *significant at $p < 0.05$

In Table 3, the calculated F-value for the difference in the achievement mean scores of treatment groups, F, of students' achievement is 0.06 while its corresponding Sig. value at df 1, 79 and 0.05 alpha level of significance is 0.00. This implies that at $p < 0.05$, the difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught the concept of chemical bonding using flipped-learning and guided-discovery learning strategies is statistically significant. That is, there is a significant difference in the academic achievement of students taught the concept of chemical bonding using flipped-learning and guided-discovery learning strategies. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Research Hypothesis Two:

There is no significant difference in the academic achievements of male and females taught with flipped-learning, and also determine the academic achievement of males and females taught with guided discovery learning strategies

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of students' posttest achievement classified by treatment groups (flipped-learning and guided-discovery learning strategies) with pretest as covariate based on gender.

Source of Variance	Sum of squares	Df	Mean	F	Sig.	Decision at 0.05 alpha
Corrected model	989.84	4	247.46	16.24	.00	Significant
Pretest (Covariate)	14.01	1	14.01	0.92	.34	Not Significant
Main effect:						
Treatment	500.51	1	500.51	32.85	.00	Significant
Gender	211.15	1	211.15	13.86	.41	Not Significant
Error	1142.91	75	15.24			
Corrected total	2132.75	79				

Source: Fieldwork, 2024 *significant at $p < 0.05$

In Table 4, the calculated F-value for the difference in the achievement mean scores of treatment groups, F-value of students' achievement based on gender is 13.86 while its corresponding Sig. value at df 1, 79 and 0.05 alpha level of significance is .41. This implies that at $p < 0.05$, the difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught the concept of chemical bonding using flipped-learning and guided-discovery learning strategies is statistically significant. That is, there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught the concept of chemical bonding using flipped-learning and Guided-discovery learning strategies based on gender. Hence, the null hypothesis was retained.

Research Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the academic achievements of male and females taught with flipped-learning, and also determine the academic achievement of males and females taught with guided discovery learning strategies

Table 5: ANCOVA on Interactive effect of treatment and gender with pretest as covariate

Source of Variance	Sum of squares	Df	Mean	F	Sig.	Decision at 0.05 alpha
Corrected model	989.84	4	247.46	16.24	.00	Significant
Pretest	14.01	1	14.01	0.92	.34	Not Significant
(Covariate)						
Main effect:						
Treatment	500.51	1	500.51	32.85	.00	Significant
Gender	211.15	1	211.15	13.86	.41	Not Significant
2-way interaction						
Treatment*Gender	6.25	1	6.25	0.41	.52	Not Significant
Error	1142.91	75	15.24			
Corrected total	2132.75	79				

*Significant at $p < .05$ R Squared = .464 (Adjusted R Squared = .436)

As shown in Table 5, the calculated F-value for the interaction effect of learning strategies and gender on students' academic achievement in chemical bonding was 0.41, while its corresponding Sig. value at df 1, 79 and 0.05 alpha level of significance is .52. Consequently, at $p < 0.05$, interaction effect of learning strategies and gender on students' academic achievement in chemical bonding was not statistically significant. That is, there was no significant interaction effect of learning strategies and gender on students' academic achievement taught the concept of chemical bonding. Hence, the null hypothesis was retained.

Considering research question three; what is the interaction effect of learning strategies and gender on students' academic achievement taught the concept of chemical bonding?

The observations from the results in Table 5 show that the interaction effect of learning strategies and gender on students' academic achievement taught the concept of chemical bonding contributed only 44% to the observed variation in students' achievement.

Discussion of Findings

Findings of the study on the academic achievement of students taught the concept of Chemical bonding using flipped-learning and guided-discovery learning strategies showed that students taught the concept of Chemical bonding using guided-discovery learning strategy performed better than those taught using flipped-learning strategies. This can be attributed to the fact that guided-discovery learning strategy encouraged active learning, allowing students to explore and discover concepts through hands-on activities, which lead to better understanding. It also encourages personalized learning, enabling students to learn at their own pace and focus on areas where they need improvement. This finding is in line with Ekiugbo (2024) who found that students taught using guided-discovery had a higher mean achievement score compared to those taught using discussion and lecture methods.

The findings of the study showed that there was a significant difference in the academic achievement of students taught the concept of chemical bonding using flipped-learning and guided-discovery learning strategies. This finding is in line with Afolabi (2018) and Oghenovo (2018) in their separate studies found that there was a significant difference between the groups. Findings of the study on the academic achievement on male and female students taught the concept of chemical bonding using flipped-learning and guided-discovery learning strategies showed that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught the concept of chemical bonding using flipped-learning and guided-discovery learning strategies based on gender. This can be attributed to prior knowledge and experience in the subject matter. Student motivation and teacher effectiveness in implementing either strategies can influence learning outcomes. This finding is in line with Eden, Tofi, Umoetuk and Charles (2023); Ekiugbo (2024) in their separate studies found that there was no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students when taught chemistry concepts.

Findings of the study on interaction effect of learning strategies and gender on students' academic achievement taught the concept of chemical bonding showed that there is no significant interaction effect of learning strategies and gender on students' academic achievement taught the concept of chemical bonding. This may be due to the fact that the learning strategies used in the study may be equally effective for both males and females, resulting in no significant interaction effect. This finding is in line with Moneke and Nwanneka (2024) who found no significant interaction effect of gender and teaching methods on students' academic achievement

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that guided-discovery learning strategy was most effective in enhancing students' achievement in the concept of chemical bonding. However, the study also found that there is no significant difference and interaction between the mean achievement scores of students taught using the flipped and guided-discovery learning strategies. This suggests that both strategies can be effective in teaching chemical bonding, but the guided discovery approach may have a slight edge.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, it was recommended that;

1. Teachers of Chemistry should be encouraged to adopt Guided-discovery learning strategy.
2. Guided-discovery learning strategy which is purposeful and efficient should be used in teaching chemical bonding to enable students participate actively.
3. Education stakeholders should organize conferences, seminars and workshops to acquaint teachers of the usefulness of Guided-discovery learning strategy to enhance teaching and learning.
4. Comparative studies can be conducted to compare the effectiveness of different teaching strategies including guided-discovery, flipped and traditional approaches.
5. Longitudinal studies can be conducted to explore the long-term effects of guided-discovery learning strategies on students' achievement and retention of chemical bonding concept.
6. Further studies can be conducted to replicate the findings of this research and explore the effectiveness of guided-discovery learning strategies in different contexts.

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